

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

Study of Prevalence and Clinical Spectrum of Septic Acute Kidney Injury (Saki) in Steroid Responsive Nephrotic Syndrome

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Abstract: Systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) insult in the nephrotic background initiates interplay between inflammation and oxidative stress, leading to septic acute kidney injury (SAKI). The reported prevalence of AKI in last century is 30% in nephrotic syndrome. Most paediatric studies are related to AKI in nephrotic syndrome while there is hardly any data on SAKI in steroid-responsive nephrotic syndrome. The present study was conducted to study the prevalence and clinical profile of SAKI in nephrotic syndrome. It was prospective observational study among children upto 12 years of age. pRIFLE and KDIGO criteria was used for AKI staging while SIRS criteria helped to analyse different categories of sepsis (Sepsis, Severe sepsis and Septic shock). Among the total 235 admitted steroid responsive nephrotic patients, 64 patients (27.23%) developed AKI while 59 of them had features of SAKI. So, the proportion of SAKI was 92.10% (59 of 64). Among 59 SAKI patients, 38 children (64.4%) developed AKI: pRIFLE stage R, 12 (20.3%) in stage I, 8 (13.6%) in stage F and 1 child (1.7%) in stage L. Among 38 patients of STAGE 1 AKI- 34 patients due to sepsis (89.5%), 3 patients- severe sepsis (7.9%) and 1 patient- septic shock (2.7%). Among 12 patients of STAGE 2 AKI: sepsis (50%), severe sepsis (33.3%) and septic shock (16.7%). Among 9 patients of STAGE-3 AKI, severe sepsis (33.3%) and septic shock (66.7%). Severity of AKI was found to be increased as per progression of sepsis to severe sepsis to septic shock. 15.3% SAKI cases were positive for blood culture (M.C.- Pneumococci) while 8.5% positive for urine culture (M.C.- E.Coli). most common presentation were Ascites (93.2%) followed by tachycardia (84.5%). 29 out of 59 patients (49.2%) developed hypertension while 23 of them developed congestive cardiac failure (39%). Clinical features included features of peritonitis or sepsis or septic shock followed by prolongation of the oliguric phase, development of hypertension, azotemia and congestive heart failure in some cases. Diuresis followed with subsidence of edema, CCF, azotemia. Hypertension persisted for variable period. Among 59 SAKI cases, majority (n=14, 23.7%) was frequent relapse nephrotic syndrome (FRNS) followed by 1st relapse (18.7%), 2nd relapse (18.7%). Regarding contributory factors, 52.4 % patients (31 out of 59) had features of hypovolemia and among them 27 patients discharged and 4 patients died. 6 patients out of 59 SAKI patients (10.17%) had prior usage of nephrotoxic drugs and among them only 1 patient died. We found that 4 out of 55 patients (7.27%) had features of relapse after 6 months, while 6 patients (10.91%) remained hypertensive as well as 2 patients developed CKD (3.64%). Sepsis and SAKI were the most important complications of steroid responsive nephrotic syndrome. Duration of hospitalisation, requirement of ICU, Ventilatory support and inotropes use are more among SAKI patients than nephrotic syndrome without SAKI.

Keywords: Sepsis, AKI, SAKI, Nephrotic syndrome

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